

Chelate Formation between Thorium(IV) and *p*-Nitrobenzene-azochromotropic Acid (Chromotrope 2B) : Spectrophotometric and Electrical Conductance Studies

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Spectrophotometric and electrical conductance studies have been made with a view to investigating the composition and stability of the chelate formed between thorium (IV) and *p*-nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid (Chromotrope 2B). The composition of the purple-coloured chelate ($\lambda_{\max}$ 550 $m\mu$), as established by a number of methods, comes out to be 1:2 (metal: chelating agent). The chelate is stable between pH 3.2 and 7.2. Tentative suggestions on the position of the chelate rings have been made.

The use of Chromotrope 2B (colour index 16575; abbreviated here as CTB) as a chelatochromic indicator in complexometric titrations and the applications of its chromogenic properties have been described by various workers. In addition to the many well-known chelate-forming reactions of Chromotrope 2B, it has recently been observed by Dey and co-workers¹ to form very stable coloured chelates in aqueous solution with scandium, yttrium, lanthanum, neodymium, and other lanthanons. Studies on the nature, composition, and stability of the above metal chelates are already in progress.

Banerji and Dey² studied the formation of a violet-coloured chelate between Th(IV) and Chromotrope 2B by the method of continued variations, employing absorbance measurements. Often, in the study of such chelate-forming systems, it is profitable to employ several methods for the elucidation of the nature of the metal chelates formed and with this idea in view, a reinvestigation of the thorium-CTB chelate has been carried out, using the method of continued variations (with electrical conductance measurements), mole-ratio method³, and the slope-ratio method⁴ (both using absorbance measurements). The present communication describes the results of these studies.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagent and standard solutions were prepared and standardised according to Banerji and Dey². A 0.5% solution of dextrin in water was used as a protective colloid. All other chemicals used were of the analytical grade.

A Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer, operated by a Doran's mains unit connected to 220V/50 cycles a.c. mains, further stabilised by a constant voltage transformer, was

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1. Srivastava *et al.*, unpublished work.
2. Banerji and Dey, *this Journal*, 1961, **38**, 139.
3. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
4. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.

employed for carrying out measurements of absorbance. At wave lengths of 625 $m\mu$ or below, the blue sensitive phototube was used and above this, the red sensitive phototube. The phototube circuit was kept at maximum sensitivity and under these conditions, the slit width corresponded to very nominal band widths. Matched glass cells of 10 mm thickness were used and the readings were recorded against distilled water blanks.

Measurements of electrical conductance were done with a Leeds and Northrup Kohlrausch slidewire with an audio-frequency oscillator in the circuit, operated on the same mains. and using a dip-type measuring cell having a cell constant 0.580.

Hydrogen-ion concentration of the solutions was measured, using a Leeds and Northrup direct reading pH-indicator.

Procedure.—The studies were performed in an air-conditioned room maintained at $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$. All the solutions and mixtures were thermostated at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.01^{\circ}$ for about an hour before use. The final volume of all the mixtures prepared for the measurements was kept 50 ml. All experiments were performed at pH 4.5 ± 0.2 and the individual solutions and mixtures were adjusted to this pH by addition of HCl or NaOH. Ionic strength was also kept constant at 0.1M, wherever mentioned, by addition of ammonium nitrate. Dextrin solution (0.5%) was used as a peptising agent, when at some concentrations, the thorium—CTB lake tended to precipitate.

In the mole-ratio method, a series of solutions was prepared, keeping the concentration of the reagent constant and with increasing molar ratios of the metal to the reagent (or *vice versa*). Absorbances were then plotted against the concentration ratios.

Two series of solutions, one containing a constant excess of the reagent with varying concentrations of the metal and the other, *vice versa*, were prepared for the slope-ratio method. In both of these methods, it was preferred to record the readings of absorbance against distilled water blanks instead of a reagent blank for so many obvious reasons.

DISCUSSION

Nature of Complexes formed.—As observed by Banerji and Dey², the region of maximum absorbance of mixtures containing 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4 ratios of thorium to Chromotrope 2B lies at 550 $m\mu$ at pH 4.5. It is thus concluded that only one chelate is formed in solution under these conditions of study. The dye at this pH has λ_{max} 520 $m\mu$.

Stoichiometry of the Components.—The ratio of metal to the reagent in the complex has been established by three different methods. The results by the method of continued variations, employing electrical conductance measurements, are summarised in Table I, where c stands for the metal ion concentration and c' for that of the reagent ($p = c'/c$).

TABLE I

Fig. No.	Curve No.	$c \times 10^4$.	p .	Peak at volume of thorium chloride.	Composition of the chelate Th (iv): CTB.
.1	A	6.66M	1.00	16.7 ml	1 : 2
	B	5.00	1.00	16.7	1 : 2
	C	3.33	1.00	16.7	1 : 2

FIG. 1

The results obtained by the mole-ratio method (Fig. 2 and 3) and by the slope-ratio method (Fig. 4 and 5) also corroborate the same composition for the chelate which may hence be represented as $\text{Th}(\text{CTB})_2$.

Effect of Hydrogen-ion Concentration on the Stability of the Chelate.—The absorbances of mixtures containing thorium chloride and Chromotrope 2B in the ratio of 1 : 2 ($c=2.5 \times 10^5 M$; $p = 2$) at different hydrogen-ion concentrations were recorded at various wave lengths. The results show that the chelate is stable within the pH range 3.2 to 7.2. Fig. 7 supports this fact, where the region of maximum absorbance is seen to lie at 550 m μ between

the above mentioned pH values. The variation in the absorbance of the chelate at $550 m\mu$ with change in pH is shown in Fig. 6.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

Structure of the Chelate.—Sommer⁵ studied the shift in the region of maximum absorbance of Chromotrope 2B with change in hydrogen-ion concentration of the medium. On the basis of the shift of λ_{max} of the dye as a result of chelation in the present case and on the basis of the investigations of Sommer and co-workers, it may be suggested that chelation occurs between the phenolic oxygens (*vide infra*).

5. *Chem. Listy*, 1956, 50, 1728; Proc. Symp. Chem. Co-ord. Compounds, Agra, 1959; 1960(3), 200.

Conc. of variable comp. $\times 10^6 M$.

FIG. 4

Conc. of variable comp. $\times 10^6 M$.

FIG. 5

$\rightarrow pH$

FIG. 6

Experiments were performed to ascertain the ionic nature of the chelate on the basis of the structure, shown below. The chelate was found to be neutral, as shown by the non-adsorption of the colour of the same by both 120 (H) and 45 (OH) varieties of Amberlite

IR ion-exchange resins. Thus it is evident that all the four sulphonic acid groups remain undissociated in the molecule as suggested in the structure below:

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